

Effects of Cashew Apple Silage Supplementation on Feed Intake and Growth Performance of Bach Thao Goats

Nguyen Thi Thu Hien ✉

Institute of Green and Sustainable Technology, Thu Dau Mot University, Vietnam

Ngo Huynh Bao Trinh

A.S.T.A Production and Trading Company Limited, Vietnam

Article History:

Received: 23.02.2026 Revised: 02.03.2026 Accepted: 04.03.2026 Published: 05.03.2026

Abstract

This study evaluated the effects of supplementing cashew apple silage in the diet of Bach Thao goats on feed intake and growth performance under practical production conditions. Twenty-four goats aged 5–7 months were arranged in a completely randomized design for 90 days, including a control diet (fresh elephant grass and compound feed) and a treatment diet supplemented with cashew apple silage. Daily feed intake was recorded to estimate metabolizable energy (ME) and crude protein (CP) intake, while body weight, body length, and chest girth were measured at 15-day intervals. Results showed that goats readily accepted the silage-based diet. Intake of cashew apple silage increased from 0.50 kg/day at the beginning to 1.35 kg/day at day 90, accompanied by increases in fresh elephant grass intake (from 1.35 to 1.82 kg/day) and compound feed (from 0.10 to 0.20 kg/day). Consequently, ME intake from cashew apple silage increased from 332.52 to 892.81, and CP from 0.05% to 1.45%. From day 60 onward, goats in the treatment group showed significantly higher body weight than the control group (14.75 vs. 13.53 kg at day 60; 16.50 vs. 15.60 kg at day 90; $P < 0.05$). Chest girth was also greater in the treatment group at day 90 (57.08 vs. 55.55 cm), while body length increased similarly in both groups. These findings demonstrate that cashew apple silage is a palatable and nutritionally effective feed resource for Bach Thao goats. Utilizing cashew apple, an abundant agricultural by-product, as livestock feed highlights its value in circular agriculture by transforming waste into useful nutrition, thereby improving sustainability and reducing feeding costs in tropical goat production systems.

Keywords: *Bach Thao goats, Growth performance, Nutrient intake, Silage feeding, Tropical goat production.*

Suggested citation: Hien, N.T.T., & Trinh, N.H.B (2026). Effects of Cashew Apple Silage Supplementation on Feed Intake and Growth Performance of Bach Thao Goats. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 4(2), 86-93. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2026.4\(2\).07](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2026.4(2).07)

Introduction

Feed resource availability is a critical constraint in goat production systems in tropical countries, where seasonal fluctuations in forage supply directly affect animal growth and productivity. In Vietnam, prolonged dry periods and irregular rainfall patterns often result in shortages of fresh green fodder, compelling farmers to rely on low-

quality crop residues or expensive commercial feeds. These limitations highlight the need for practical feed preservation techniques that can ensure year-round nutritional supply while utilizing locally available agricultural by-products.

Silage technology has been widely recognized as an effective method for preserving moist plant

materials and agro-industrial residues through lactic fermentation. Properly prepared silage improves feed storability, palatability, and digestibility, and has been successfully applied in ruminant production systems worldwide. In tropical regions, materials such as corn stalks, cassava pulp, and fruit processing residues represent abundant resources for silage production. Despite these advantages, the application of silage feeding in small-scale goat farming in Vietnam remains limited, and scientific evaluations of its effects on goat performance under local conditions are still insufficient.

Bach Thao goats are an indigenous Vietnamese breed well adapted to hot and humid environments, characterized by good disease resistance, moderate body size, and suitability for smallholder production systems (Nguyen T.T.H, 2024). This breed plays an important role in rural livelihoods due to its adaptability and low management requirements. However, most feeding practices for Bach Thao goats still depend heavily on fresh forage availability, making growth performance vulnerable to seasonal feed shortages. Research focusing specifically on nutritional strategies to improve growth performance of Bach Thao goats is relatively scarce, particularly in relation to preserved feeds such as silage.

Previous studies on silage feeding have primarily focused on cattle or crossbred goats, with limited attention given to pure Bach Thao goats. Moreover, existing reports often emphasize feed composition or fermentation quality rather than assessing animal growth responses under practical feeding conditions. This creates a knowledge gap regarding the suitability and effectiveness of silage-based diets for improving growth parameters in this indigenous goat breed.

Therefore, this study was conducted to evaluate the growth performance of Bach Thao goats fed diets supplemented with silage derived from locally available agricultural materials. The findings are expected to provide scientific evidence supporting the application of silage feeding as a sustainable nutritional strategy for Bach Thao goat production in tropical environments.

Materials and Methods

Research Materials

Bach Thao goats aged from 5 to 7 months. Silage made from cashew apples. Fresh elephant grass. Commercial concentrate feed (Tongwei, produced by Tongwei Vietnam Co., Ltd. at Tan Huong Industrial Park, Chau Thanh District, Tien Giang Province).

Experimental Design

Bach Thao goats were allocated into two experimental groups under a completely randomized design. The control group was fed fresh elephant grass and commercial concentrate. Treatment group received a diet consisting of cashew apple silage, fresh elephant grass, and concentrate.

Each group consisted of four goats and was replicated twice. The feeding arrangement and dietary composition for each treatment are presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

Table 1. Experimental Arrangement for the Control Group of Bach Thao Goats

Feed type	Feed amount (kg)	Feeding time (hour)
Compound feed	0,5	6
Fresh elephant grass	2	10
Compound feed	0,5	14
Fresh elephant grass	2	16

Table 2. Experimental Layout Table for Treatment Groups in Bach Thao Goats

Feed type	Feed amount (kg)	Feeding time (hour)
Compound feed and Silage	0,1 and 1	6
Fresh elephant grass	2	10
Compound feed and Silage	0,1 and 1	14
Fresh elephant grass	2	16

After each day, the leftover feed was weighed again at 5:30 a.m. the following morning. The amount of feed consumed was calculated (kg/treatment group/day). Based on the feed intake, the feed requirement of Bach Thao goats was determined (kg/treatment group/day).

Data Processing

Feed intake

$$M = M_t - M_s \quad (1)$$

M: feed intake

M_t : feed offered before feeding

M_s : feed refused (leftover)

$$\text{ME/goat/day} = \text{amount of feed consumed} \times \text{ME per kg} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{CP/goat/day} = \text{amount of feed consumed} \times \text{CP per kg} \quad (3)$$

The ME and CP (%) values of the compound feed were obtained from the manufacturer's label. The values for fresh elephant grass were based on the Vietnamese feed composition tables for livestock. The values for silage were provided by the Center for Animal Husbandry Biotechnology – Southern Institute of Animal Husbandry.

Determination of Growth Rate in Bach Thao Goats

Parameters monitored

Body measurements included body diagonal length and heart girth.

Body diagonal length: measured from the prominent point of the humerus at the shoulder to the rear prominence of the ischial tuberosity (measured with a measuring tape, unit: cm).

Heart girth: the circumference of the chest just behind the scapula (measured with a measuring tape, unit: cm).

Goats were weighed and measured every 15 days in the morning using a Nhon Hoa dial scale (unit: kg) with an error margin of ± 50 g. Measurements were taken continuously for 3 months.

Time of weighing and measuring: 5:30 a.m. (before feeding).

Cumulative growth

Cumulative growth refers to the increase in body weight, size, and volume of part or the whole body of Bach Thao goats at a given time.

Body weight was recorded in kilograms using a dial scale.

Cumulative growth in body weight and body length of Bach Thao goats was determined by weighing in the morning before feeding. Each weighing and measurement was conducted at 15-day intervals.

Weight gain (kg/goat/15 days) was calculated as: Weight gain = later weight – previous weight.

Body length and heart girth were measured in the morning before feeding using a measuring tape (cm).

Increase in body length (cm/goat/15 days) was calculated as: Increase in body length = later measurement – previous measurement.

Increase in heart girth (cm/goat/15 days) was calculated as: Increase in heart girth = later measurement – previous measurement.

Results

The results of the survey on the daily feed consumption of Bach Thao goats when supplemented with fermented cashew nuts are shown in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3. Results of the Amount of Goat Feed Consumed per Day in the Control Group (CON)

Day	Feed type	$\bar{X} \pm SD$ (kg)	ME(Mcal/kg)	CP(%)
0	Fresh elephant grass	1,38 \pm 0,08	215,28	2,82
	Compound feed	0,62 \pm 0,06	1798,00	0,50
15	Fresh elephant grass	1,42 \pm 0,55	221,52	2,90
	Compound feed	0,69 \pm 0,12	2001,00	0,55

30	Fresh elephant grass	1,62±0,96	252,72	3,30
	Compound feed	0,70±0,21	2030,00	0,56
45	Fresh elephant grass	1,63±0,92	252,72	3,30
	Compound feed	0,73±0,29	2117,00	0,58
60	Fresh elephant grass	1,79±0,37	279,24	3,67
	Compound feed	0,77±0,31	2233,00	0,96
75	Fresh elephant grass	1,85±0,44	290,16	3,79
	Compound feed	0,81±0,37	2349,00	0,65
90	Fresh elephant grass	1,88±0,41	293,28	3,85
	Compound feed	0,86±0,41	2494,00	0,69

Table 4. Results of Daily Goat Feed Consumption in Treatment Group (TM) (cashew apple silage)

Day	Feed type	$\bar{X}\pm SD(\text{kg})$	ME(Mcal/kg)	CP(%)
0	Fresh elephant grass	1,35±0,21	210,61	3,37
	Compound feed	0,1±0,02	290,01	0,08
	Cashew apple silage	0,5±0,02	332,52	0,05
15	Fresh elephant grass	1,41±0,16	219,96	3,52
	Compound feed	0,1±0,03	290,03	0,08
	Cashew apple silage	0,75±0,04	498,75	0,77
30	Fresh elephant grass	1,45±0,52	226,22	3,62
	Compound feed	0,1±0,02	290,13	0,08
	Cashew apple silage	0,80±0,03	532,31	0,82
45	Fresh elephant grass	1,6±0,26	249,62	3,65
	Compound feed	0,15±0,05	435,03	0,12
	Cashew apple silage	1,01±0,05	671,65	1,04
60	Fresh elephant grass	1,79±0,37	279,24	4,45
	Compound feed	0,15±0,03	435,14	0,12
	Cashew apple silage	1,21±0,06	804,65	1,25
75	Fresh elephant grass	1,88±0,23	293,28	4,75
	Compound feed	0,22±0,07	580,12	0,14
	Cashew apple silage	1,32±0,05	877,81	1,36
90	Fresh elephant grass	1,82±0,20	283,92	4,45
	Compound feed	0,2±0,11	580,23	0,16
	Cashew apple silage	1,35±0,04	892,81	1,45

The results of monitoring the body weight and size (body length, chest circumference) of Bach Thao goats over 90 days of experimentation with feed supplemented with fermented cashew nuts are shown in Tables 5, 6 and 7.

Table 5. Results of Weight Gain Rate of Bach Thao Goats when Using Silage Feed

Day	CON (kg)	TM (kg)
0	12,00±2,62	12,38±3,42
15	12,20±2,45	12,45±3,18
30	12,48±3,13	12,80±3,21
45	12,65±3,43	13,65±3,47
60	13,53 ^a ±3,06	14,75 ^b ±3,10
75	14,93 ^a ±2,92	15,13 ^b ±2,93
90	15,60 ^a ±3,03	16,50 ^b ±2,73

Note: Mean values with different letters (a, b) in the same row show statistically significant differences between the two groups (P<0.05).

Table 6. Results of Monitoring the Body Length Growth Rate of Bach Thao Goats when Using Silage Feed

Day	CON (cm)	TM (cm)
0	49,38±0,29	49,50 ±0,19
15	51,63±1,1	52,88±0,95
30	55,25±1,50	54,13±0,95
45	57,38±0,95	58,81±1,60
60	60,50±1,29	61,25±1,19
75	63,63±0,48	64,02±0,41
90	66,75±0,29	66,83±0,48

Note: Mean values with different letters (a, b) in the same row show statistically significant differences between the two groups (P<0.05).

Table 7. Results of Monitoring the Chest Circumference Growth Rate of Bach Thao Goats when Using Silage Feed

Day	CON (cm)	TM (cm)
0	42,30±0,16	47,30 ±0,29
15	44,50±0,19	44,48±0,24
30	47,10±0,14	46,48±0,30
45	49,03±0,24	48,35±0,32
60	51,15±0,32	51,25±0,42
75	53,05 ^a ±0,35	56,05 ^b ±0,63
90	55,55 ^a ±0,48	57,08 ^b ±0,45

Note: Mean values with different letters (a, b) in the same row show statistically significant differences between the two groups ($P < 0.05$).

Discussion

The results (Table 3) showed a gradual increase in feed intake of both compound feed and fresh elephant grass throughout the 90-day experimental period in Bach Thao goats. The average consumption of compound feed increased from 1.38 kg at day 0 to 1.88 kg at day 90, while fresh elephant grass intake rose from 0.62 kg to 0.86 kg over the same period. This upward trend, nearly 40% for both feed types, reflects the normal physiological pattern of growing goats, in which increased body weight leads to greater maintenance and growth requirements, thereby stimulating higher voluntary feed intake. The consistent rise in intake also indicates good palatability of the diet and an absence of digestive disturbances, suggesting that the animals adapted well to the experimental ration.

Correspondingly, the calculated metabolizable energy (ME) and crude protein (CP) intake per day increased over time. ME values derived from compound feed increased from 215.28 to 293.28, while those from fresh elephant grass increased from 1798.00 to 2494.00. Similarly, CP intake rose from 2.82 to 3.85 for compound feed and from 0.50 to 0.69 for elephant grass. This increase was not due to changes in feed composition but rather to the greater quantity of feed consumed as the goats grew. The higher absolute intake of energy and protein in later stages of the trial demonstrates that the diet adequately met the increasing nutritional demands associated with rapid growth.

The standard deviation values were relatively higher during the early stages (days 30–45), indicating variability in feed consumption among individuals during the adaptation phase. However, from day 60 onward, the variation became more stable, suggesting uniform feeding behavior and better synchronization of rumen microbial activity across the herd. This stabilization is an important indicator of successful dietary adaptation and rumen function.

Overall, the simultaneous increase in feed intake, ME, and CP throughout the experimental period confirms that the combination of compound feed and fresh elephant grass was nutritionally appropriate for growing Bach Thao goats. The diet supported continuous growth without signs of nutritional deficiency and provides practical evidence for establishing feeding standards for Bach Thao goats according to growth stage.

The results (Table 4) indicate a clear increase in total feed intake over the 90-day experimental period when Bach Thao goats were fed a diet consisting of fresh elephant grass, compound feed, and cashew apple silage. The intake of fresh elephant grass increased from 1.35 kg at day 0 to 1.82 kg at day 90. Similarly, cashew apple silage consumption rose markedly from 0.50 kg to 1.35 kg, while compound feed intake increased from 0.10 kg to 0.20 kg. This trend demonstrates a progressive increase in voluntary feed intake as body weight and growth demand increased. Notably, the sharp rise in cashew apple silage consumption suggests good palatability and acceptance of this unconventional feed resource by the goats.

The metabolizable energy (ME) and crude protein (CP) intake calculated from the consumed feeds also increased substantially throughout the experiment. ME values associated with cashew apple silage increased from 332.52 to 892.81, while those from fresh elephant grass rose from 210.61 to 283.92. The contribution of compound feed to ME also increased due to greater intake in later stages. A similar pattern was observed for CP intake, where CP from fresh elephant grass increased from 3.37% to 4.45%, and CP from cashew apple silage increased consistently from 0.05%

to 1.45%. These increases were driven by higher feed consumption rather than changes in feed composition, indicating that the goats were able to obtain greater absolute amounts of energy and protein to meet the demands of rapid growth.

The standard deviation values were relatively higher during the early and middle stages (days 30–45), reflecting individual differences in adaptation to the inclusion of cashew apple silage in the diet. From day 60 onward, the variation decreased, indicating more uniform feeding behavior and improved rumen adaptation to the silage-based diet. This stabilization suggests that rumen microbial populations had effectively adjusted to the fermentation products present in cashew apple silage.

Overall, the simultaneous increase in intake of fresh elephant grass, compound feed, and especially cashew apple silage, along with the corresponding rise in ME and CP intake, demonstrates that cashew apple silage can be effectively utilized as a feed resource for Bach Thao goats. The diet supported continuous growth, showed good acceptability, and provided adequate energy and protein throughout the experimental period. These findings highlight the potential of fermented cashew apple as an alternative feed ingredient in goat production systems.

The results in Table 5 show that body weight of Bach Thao goats increased steadily in both the control (CON) and treatment (TM) groups over the 90-day period. However, from day 60 onward, goats fed the diet supplemented with cashew apple silage (TM) exhibited significantly higher body weights than those in the control group ($P < 0.05$). At day 90, the TM group reached 16.50 kg compared to 15.60 kg in the CON group. This indicates that the inclusion of cashew apple silage in the diet provided additional nutrients that enhanced growth performance. The absence of significant differences in the early stages (0–45 days) suggests an adaptation period to the silage feed, while the clear divergence after day 60 reflects improved nutrient utilization and growth response once rumen microorganisms adapted to the fermented feed source.

Table 6 demonstrates a continuous increase in body diagonal length in both groups throughout the experiment. Although differences between the CON and TM groups were not consistently statistically significant at all time points, the TM group generally showed slightly greater body length values, particularly from day 45 onward. By day 90, both groups reached nearly similar values (66.83 cm in TM and 66.75 cm in CON), indicating that skeletal growth occurred steadily in all goats regardless of treatment. The relatively small differences suggest that body length is less sensitive to dietary supplementation compared to body weight, as skeletal growth is influenced more by genetic factors and overall nutrition rather than specific feed components.

The data in Table 7 reveal notable differences in chest circumference between the two groups, particularly at later stages. While early measurements showed fluctuations, from day 75 onward the TM group displayed significantly larger chest circumference than the CON group ($P < 0.05$). At day 90, chest circumference in the TM group reached 57.08 cm compared to 55.55 cm in the CON group. Chest girth is closely associated with body mass, muscle development, and overall body condition; therefore, this result supports the findings in Table 5 that cashew apple silage supplementation improved growth performance. The greater chest development in the TM group indicates enhanced tissue deposition and better body conformation as a result of improved nutrient intake and utilization.

The results of the present study are consistent with previous investigations evaluating growth performance and selected rumen and serum biochemical parameters in sheep fed hay, silage, or maize silage as forage sources (Bernes et al., 2008; Bernes & Stengärde, 2012). Bernes et al. (2008) reported that the use of silage as a forage source did not affect ruminal pH, NH_3 concentration, or the concentrations of acetate, propionate, and butyrate in rumen fluid. Similarly, the type of fresh forage offered had no significant effect on serum glucose, total protein, or albumin concentrations (Bernes et al., 2008).

Bernes and Stengärde (2012) observed no significant differences in live weight gain or feed

intake between sheep fed hay and those fed silage, although slightly higher live weight gain and feed intake were recorded in animals receiving hay. In agreement with these findings, several studies in cattle have reported no differences in body weight or average daily gain when animals were fed high-quality fresh forage or silage (Ayaşan et al., 2012); silage, maize silage, or grass plus maize silage (Juniper et al., 2005); alfalfa and maize silage (Kirkland & Patterson, 2006); or maize meal and ensiled fodder beet (Browne et al., 2005).

In Vietnam, studies on the use of ensiled cassava pulp have also demonstrated positive effects in ruminants (Nguyen H. Q. & Nguyen X. B., 2008; Nguyen H. V. et al., 2008). More recently, research investigating the effects of silage on growth parameters of Phan Rang sheep reported normal growth rates when silage was included in the diet (Nguyen D. T. et al., 2021). At day 90, body weight ranged from 19.0 to 19.9 kg across treatments, with no statistically significant differences ($P > 0.05$) among treatment groups or compared with the control. Silage feeding also did not affect hematological and blood physiological parameters in Phan Rang sheep (Nguyen B. P. et al., 2023). Recent research by Nguyen T.T.H. also showed that silage feed did not affect the physiological and biochemical blood parameters of Saanen goats (Nguyen T.T.H., 2024; Hien, N.T.T. 2024)

Taken together, the findings from previous studies and the present research indicate that the use of ensiled maize, cassava, and cashew apple as forage sources does not adversely affect the health status of Bach Thao goats.

Conclusion

Supplementation with cashew apple silage in the diet of Bach Thao goats increased voluntary feed intake, improved metabolizable energy and crude protein supply, and resulted in significantly higher body weight and chest circumference from day 60 onward compared to the control group. Goats adapted well to the silage-based diet without digestive disturbances, indicating good palatability and rumen adaptation.

These findings confirm that cashew apple silage is a nutritionally effective feed resource for Bach Thao goats. Importantly, the use of cashew apple—a major agricultural by-product often discarded—demonstrates clear potential for converting waste into valuable livestock feed. This contributes to circular agriculture by reducing environmental waste, lowering feed costs, and promoting sustainable goat production in tropical farming systems.

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank the the Center for Research and Development of Large Livestock and the veterinarians and livestock staff at the center for supporting this research.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Ayaşan, T., Gök, K., Asarkaya, A., Hizli, H., Görgülü, M., Karakozak, E., Coşkun, M.A., & Seğmenoglu, M.S. (2012). The effects of corn silage and sugar beet pulp on fattening performance, blood parameters, and carcass characteristics of bulls. *Journal of Faculty of Agriculture, University of Süleyman Demirel*, 7, 64-73.
- Bernes, G., & Stengärde, L. (2012). Sheep fed only silage or silage supplemented with concentrates: Effects on ewe performance and blood metabolites. *Small Ruminant Research*, 102(1-3), 108-113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smallrumres.2011.09.014>
- Bernes, G., Hetta, M., & Martinsson, K. (2008). Effects of harvest date of timothy (*Pbleum pratense*) on its nutritive value, voluntary silage intake, and liveweight gain of lambs. *Grass and Forage Science*, 63, 212-220. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2494.2008.00634.x>
- Browne E.M., Juniper D.T., Bryant M.J., & Beever D.E. (2005). Apparent digestibility and nitrogen utilization of diets based on maize and grass silage fed to beef steers. *Ani. Feed. Sci. Technol.*, 119, 55-68. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2494.2005.00477.x>

Hien, N.T.T. (2024). Correlation of Silage Feeds to Blood Biochemical Parameters in Saanen Goats. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(5), 585-592. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(5\).56](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(5).56)

Juniper, D. T., Browne, E. M., Fisher, A. V., Bryant, M. J., Nute, G. R., & Beaver, D. E. (2005). Intake, growth, and meat quality of steers given diets based on varying proportions of maize silage and grass silage. *Journal of Animal Science*, 81(1), 159-170. <https://doi.org/10.2527/2005.8111159x>

Kirkland, R. M., & Patterson, D. C. (2006). The effect of quality of grass and maize silage on the intake and performance of beef cattle. *Livestock Science*, 100(1), 179-188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livsci.2005.08.005>

Nguyen, B. P., Nguyen, D. T., & Nguyen, T. T. H. (2023). Blood physiological indicators of Phan Rang sheep when using silage. *National Conference on Biotechnology Science*, 1426-1431.

Nguyen, D. T., Ngo, H. B. T., Le, M. T., & Nguyen, T. T. H. (2021). Survey of growth indicators of Phan Rang sheep when using silage. *Thu Dau Mot University Journal of Science*, 2(51), 40-47.

Nguyen, H. Q., & Nguyen, X. B. (2008). Effects of cassava silage supplementation on feed intake, digestibility, and some rumen environmental parameters of sheep fed with rice straw. *Hue University Journal of Science*, 46, 97-105.

Nguyen, H. V., Nguyen, X. B., & Bui, V. L. (2008). Evaluation of nutritional value of industrial cassava silage with additives for ruminant feed. *Hue University Journal of Science*, 46, 129-135.

Nguyen, T. T. H. (2024). Blood biochemical index of goats when using silage. *Journal of Animal Husbandry Science and Technology – Vietnam Animal Husbandry Association*, 300(7), 44-49.